

Assessing Monitoring and Evaluation Practices for Sustainable Building Projects: Case of the Convention Facility at Kenya School of Government, Embu County, Kenya

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Abstract

Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) is an integral component that supports project success and performance. M&E provides a structured framework for tracking progress, assessing outcomes and making informed decisions and adjustment strategies needed to attain project goals. This study assessed how M&E practices (capacity building, funding, stakeholder participation, dissemination of M&E results) impact the sustainability of building construction projects with a special focus on the Convention Facility at the Kenya School of Government in Embu County, Kenya. Both sustainability and stakeholder theories anchored the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. From a target population of 180, simple random sampling was used to select a sample size of 123. Data was collected using structured questionnaires and interview guide. Reliability was determined through split-half method. Narrative data was analysed qualitatively, descriptive and inferential statistics were used in quantitative data analysis. F-statistic test was adopted 95% confidence interval. The findings showed that funding of M&E had the strongest relationship ($r=0.82$), followed by capacity building ($r=0.37$), stakeholder participation ($r=0.25$) and dissemination of M&E findings ($r=0.21$). The null hypothesis was therefore rejected as the prevailing evidence indicated that these M&E practices significantly influence the sustainability of the project. The model explained 70% of the variation in the project's sustainability ($R^2=0.70$). Government and project managers should therefore prioritize on funding of M&E interventions while investing in capacity building for stakeholders, enhancing their participation in M&E processes and ensuring effective dissemination of M&E findings for greater project sustainability.

Keywords: *capacity-building, funding, stakeholder-participation, dissemination, sustainability*

JEL Classification codes: *O22, H43.*

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Introduction

Building construction projects are vital for socioeconomic development as they facilitate resource mobility, fostering city and town growth (International Finance Corporation, 2020). These projects, including transport, water management, power generation, telecommunications and educational facilities, serve as catalysts for job creation. Educational construction projects, such as conference facilities, are designed to support conventions, knowledge exchange, learning, and exhibitions. Depending on their purpose, these facilities may include auditoriums, cinemas, theatres, offices, and exhibition spaces. While effective planning aligned with market demands is crucial for sustainable impact, not all conference facilities achieve long-term success. Investment in conference facilities in the USA is becoming increasingly competitive and innovative, with a focus on "green thinking" approaches aimed at achieving high environmental sustainability standards (Meneghelli, 2018). Nevertheless, USA faces key challenges for conference facilities include adapting to the evolving customer demands for destinations, networking, and educational experiences. Poor monitoring and evaluation (M&E) practices have been linked to the underperformance of building projects in the USA, underscoring the importance of M&E in assessing project effectiveness and sustainability (Callistus and Clinton, 2018). In Europe, building project sustainability is advanced through innovative approaches that integrate modern technology and controlled material use, helping to mitigate factors that could hinder long-term success (Bonoli, Zanni, & Serrano-Bernardo, 2021). Successful building projects in Europe often benefit from robust M&E mechanisms throughout the project lifecycle, which contribute to effective planning and implementation. Nonetheless, just like in USA, many building construction projects in European countries face operational and maintenance challenges that threaten their sustainability. In the United Kingdom and other European countries, conference facilities in coastal resorts and cities have grown due to high tourism, stimulating the retail, hotel, and leisure sectors and generating employment. However, the popularity of these venues has led to overcrowding and environmental pollution (Juan, 2020). Additionally, the growth of the service industry through conference facilities has, in some cases, limited manufacturing sector opportunities, contributing to higher unemployment rates (Juan, 2020).

The shift to virtual meetings post-COVID-19 pandemic is reshaping the development of conference facilities, necessitating adaptation to evolving market needs in Asian Countries (Kornei, 2020). Nevertheless, Countries like Indonesia and India have reported inefficiencies in convention facility projects, posing challenges to achieving sustainable impacts (Devina, 2021). As a result, effective monitoring of both internal and external factors that could impact project sustainability has become essential. In Africa, the rising demand for knowledge exchange and expos is pushing governments to develop modern conference facilities. But African countries continue to face operational challenges including financial constraints, management issues, and workforce limitations (ADB, 2021). Specific problems are noted in South Africa and Rwanda, where facility layouts may be ineffective. In Ghana, planning and venue appeal are increasing becoming areas of concerns in building of convention facilities. In Egypt, organizational challenges and weak interpersonal relations among staff affect the sustainability of conference facilities projects (Kruger, 2016). In support of Kenya's Vision 2030 goal to enhance global competitiveness in education, research and training, the Kenyan Government initiated the construction of a convention facility at the Kenya School of Government. Launched in 2019 with a projected cost of Kenya Shillings 1 billion (6Million USD) with an aim of delivering high-quality convention services. But the project faced significant delays due to financial constraints, scheduling issues, operational risks and limited stakeholder engagement. Ineffective Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) practices are cited as a major risk to its sustainability. This study investigated the role of M&E practices including capacity building, funding, participation, and dissemination of findings in supporting the facility's long-term viability.

Problem Statement

The Government of Kenya is encountering significant challenges regarding the sustainability of its building construction projects. For instance, the convention facility project at the Kenya School of Government (KSG) in Embu County is reported to face issues such as usability concerns, insufficient skilled personnel, poor maintenance practices, budget constraints and limited stakeholder involvement, all of which jeopardize the project's completion and the achievement of its intended goals (Kenya School of Government, 2021). These challenges are hindering potential investment opportunities, as delays in meeting timeline, budget, and quality standards prevent timely access to project benefits (PMI, 2021). Although the convention facility aims to establish essential infrastructure to improve convention services and exceed client expectations, questions remain about the project's path toward sustainable completion. Previous studies have shown that capacity building in Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) can enhance project sustainability (Kithinji, 2019; Rogito, Maitho, & Nderitu, 2020). However, these studies were primarily exploratory in nature and lacked hypothesis testing. This study addresses that gap by testing hypothesis. Other research indicates that funding M&E activities boosts project effectiveness and sustainability (Murei et al., 2017; Njeru & Luketero, 2018). But these findings were contextually limited to horticulture and healthcare projects respectively. Shifting focus to the KSG convention facility project, this study also considered the role of stakeholder participation in M&E, which has been shown to facilitate informed and sustainable project decisions (Makau et al., 2018; Okul & Nyonje, 2020; Sulemana, 2018). While past studies relied mainly on secondary data or qualitative methods resulting into limited generalizability, this study relied on primary data collected from a randomized sample to increase the validity of the findings. In overcoming the contextual limitations, this study examined how M&E practices influence the sustainability of building construction projects, specifically the convention facility at the Kenya School of Government (KSG) in the settings of Embu County, Kenya.

Objective of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the influence of Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) practices on sustainability of building construction projects, with a specific focus on the convention facility at the Kenya School of Government (KSG) in Embu County, Kenya.

Research Hypothesis

The null hypothesis (Ho) stated that: There is no significant influence of Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) practices on sustainability of building construction-projects for the case of Convention Facility in Kenya School of Government (KSG) in Embu County, Kenya.

Literature Review

Previous research relevant to these studies were critically analysed in line with research variables. Under capacity building in Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) and sustainability of project, two empirical studies were examined: one by Kithinji (2019) and another by Rogito et al. (2020). Both studies suffered from methodological, contextual and generalizability limitations. Under M&E activities and sustainability of project, studies by Murei et al. (2017) and Njeru and Luketero (2018) were reviewed whereby conceptual and methodological gaps were identified, prompting this study to implement strategies to bridge these gaps. Stakeholders' participation in M&E and sustainability of project, research by Makau et al. (2018) and by Okul and Nyonje (2020) were reviewed whereby both studies were limited to secondary data. Additionally, both studies faced used broader conceptualization of the variables. This study addressed these issues by collecting primary data and refining the scope of M&E practices. Finally, knowledge-gaps for dissemination of M&E results

and sustainability of project were derived from empirical studies by Mutekhele et al. (2016) and Zulch (2014), identifying both conceptual and contextual limitations. The present study addressed these gaps by refining the concept of M&E practices and contextualizing the research within the Kenya School of Government in Embu County. Table 1 provides the summary of knowledge gaps identified in the literature

Table 1. Summary of Knowledge Gaps

Variable	Author	Findings	Knowledge Gap
Capacity building in Monitoring and Evaluation	Kithinji (2019)	Unstructured activities to build evaluation capacity which promotes project effectiveness	The explorative study did not test hypothesis. Instead, this study used regression analysis in predicting the influence of capacity building on M&E on sustainability of project
	Rogito, Maitho, and Nderitu, (2020).	Project M&E was enhanced through Capacity building which in turn enhanced sustainability of irrigation projects	The generalization of the findings was limited to irrigation projects. But this study focused on the sustainability of building construction-projects (convention facility at the Kenya School of Government, Kenya)
Funding of Monitoring and Evaluation activities	Murei, Kidombo and Gakuu (2017)	M&E budget contributed to high performance of horticulture projects	Conceptually, the study was limited to project performance and not sustainability. In overcoming the gap, this study examined how funding M&E activities contributes to the sustainability of convention facility project at the Kenya School of Government
	Njeru and Luketero (2018)	Adequate resource allocation in M&E increases effectiveness of project	Reliance on descriptive statistics only limited generalization of findings. But this study used inferential statistics in order to build evidence for generalizing the findings
Stakeholders` participation in Monitoring and Evaluation	Makau Mackenz and Nicole (2018)	Stakeholder participation enhances quality of Monitoring and Evaluations	Reliance of secondary data lowered the validity for concluding and generalizing the findings. Instead, this study relied on raw data to increase validity for generalizing the findings
	Okul and Nyonje (2020)	Stakeholder participation increases usability of Monitoring and Evaluation results	The concept of Monitoring and Evaluation was too broad. But this study narrowed down to stakeholders` participation during M&E relative to project sustainability
Dissemination of Monitoring and Evaluation results	Mutekhele, Rambo, Ongati and Nyonje, (2016).	Dissemination and use of data have no significant influence on project performance	The findings were contextually and geographically limited to Bungoma County. This shifted geographical region to convention facility project at the Kenya School of Government in Embu County, Kenya
	Zulch (2014)	Effective communication of project processes improves project outcome	The use of descriptive statistics only lowered generalizability of the findings. But this study used inferential statistics in the analysis to increase validity for generalizing the findings.

Source: Authors (2024)

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored in the theory of sustainability, supported by stakeholder theory, which emphasizes the need for a participatory monitoring process to ensure the long-term realization of project benefits.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 illustrates the linkage between the independent variables (Monitoring and Evaluation practices) and dependent variable (sustainability of convention facility project at Kenya School of Government).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Authors (2024)

Materials and Methods

This study adopted a descriptive survey. The target population comprised of 180 individuals who included: 1 Director, 6 technical officers in building (public works officer, quantity surveyor, structural engineer, architect, inspector, project manager) and 173 beneficiaries of the project. A sample of 123 participants was obtained using the Krejcie and Morgan table and was proportionally distributed within sub-populations as follows: 1 Director, 4 technical officers and 118 beneficiaries. Simple random sampling as adopted in the actual selection of respondents. Data was collected using structured questionnaires and interviews. The questionnaires were designed using 5-point Likert scale and were structured to capture quantitative responses. Instrument validity was strengthened by aligning indicators with specific questions. Reliability of the instruments was confirmed through the split-half method and accepted after Pearson's coefficient of 0.75, which exceeded the accepted threshold of $\alpha=0.7$ (Creswell, 2013). Qualitative data, including respondent views and opinions, was analyzed by transcription, coding, theme generation, summarizing and integration with descriptive statistics. Quantitative data was keyed into the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS version 28) to generate descriptive statistics (frequency, percentages, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics. While Pearson's Correlation Analysis was reliably used to establish the relationships between predictor and outcome variables, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to examine the significance of differences in means between independent and dependent variables. Regression analysis was used to evaluate the model's effectiveness in predicting project sustainability. F-statistical test was used to test the overall significance of the regression model at 95% confidence interval. The study was anchored on the following model.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon, \quad (1)$$

where:

Y is sustainability of project convention facility project at the KSG, Embu County, Kenya

X₁ is capacity building in M&E

X₂ is funding of M&E activities

X₃ is stakeholders' participation in M&E

X₄ is dissemination of M&E results

β_0 is constant, β_1, β_4 are beta coefficients for X₁..X₄ respectively, ϵ is the error term.

Results

Response Rate

Out of the 118 questionnaires disbursed, 99 were duly filled and returned. The findings indicate a return-rate of 83.9% which is far above Spector et al, (2020) minimum recommendation of 70% for scientific inquiries. Four out of five or 80% respondents were interviewed. It implies that the return rate was both adequate and acceptable. This strengthened confidence in the validity when concluding the results.

Sociodemographic Data

The gender distribution of respondents for questionnaires was as follows: 65 (56.6%) were male and 43 (43.4%) were female respondents. Interview data was collected from 2 males (50%) and 2 females (50%). It implied that the gender representation was balanced. This was significant in ensuring that the findings are not invalidated due to gender biasness. Further findings indicated that years of experience of respondents in project monitoring and evaluation (M&E) decreased in the following order of years: above 5 years 30 (30.0%), 4-5 years 25 (25.0%), 2-3 years 23 (23.0%), 1-3 years 10 (10.0%), 3-4years 7 (7.0%) and 0-1 year 5 (5.0%). Further, the finding revealed that all respondents for interviews had at least five years' experience in M&E. Thus, all respondents had enough experience to understand the implementation of the conventional facility at the Kenya School of Government so as to convey informed and valid responses.

Reliability of Research Instruments

Reliability of the instruments was established using split-half-method and Pearson's correlational analysis. The results revealed the coefficients of alpha as follows: for capacity building (0.79), funding (0.75), stakeholders' participation (0.80) and dissemination of monitoring and evaluation results (0.72). The reliability was deemed stable and acceptable since they all exceeded Creswell (2013) recommends of at least (α) value of 0.7.

Correlational Results

The relationship between Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) practices and sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County in Kenya was determine using Pearson's Product Moment Correlational Analysis. The correlation coefficients are depicted in Table 2.

Table 2. Correlational Results for the Relationship between Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) Practices and Sustainability of Convention Facility Project at KSG in Embu County, Kenya

		Sustainability of building construction-projects at KSG	Capacity building in M&E	Funding M&E activities	Stakeholders` participation in M&E	Dissemination of M&E findings
Sustainability of building construction-projects at KSG	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
	n	99				
Capacity building in M&E	Pearson Correlation	0.37**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00				
	n	99	99			
Funding M&E activities	Pearson Correlation	0.82**	0.30**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00			
	n	99	99	99		
Stakeholders` participation in M&E	Pearson`s-Correlation	0.23**	0.31**	0.14**	1	
	Signf. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.01	0.00		
	n	99	999	99	99	
Dissemination of M&E findings	Pearson Correlation	0.21**	0.24**	0.17**	0.37**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.03	0.18	0.10	0.00	
	n	99	99	99	99	99

Source: Authors (2024)

From the data shown in Table 2., the strength of the relationship between M&E practices and sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County decreased in the following order: funding Monitoring and Evaluation activities ($r=0.82$), capacity building in M&E ($r=0.37$), stakeholders` participation in M&E ($r=0.25$) and dissemination of M&E findings ($r=0.21$).

Regression Results

Sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County was regressed against Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) practices and the results are shown in Table.

Table 3. Regression Results for Sustainability of Convention Facility Project at KSG in Embu County, Kenya and M&E Practices

Model Summary									
Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics		Sig. Change		
					R ² Change	F Change	df1	df2	
1	0.83 ^a	0.70	0.68	0.16	0.70	54	4	94	0.00

a-Predictors are (Constant), capacity building, funding, stakeholders` participation, dissemination of M&E findings

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.22	4	1.31	54	0.00
	Residual	2.29	94	0.02		
	Total	7.51	98			
a Dependent Variable: Sustainability of Convention Facility Project at KSG in Embu County						
b Predictors: (Constant), capacity building in M&E, funding M&E activities, stakeholders` participation in M&E, dissemination of M&E findings						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.54	0.32		1.72	0.09
	Capacity building in M&E	0.10	0.06	0.11	1.74	0.09
	Funding M&E activities	0.63	0.05	0.77	12.78	0.00
	Stakeholders` participation in M&E	0.12	0.07	0.11	1.75	0.08
	Dissemination of M&E findings	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.24	0.82

Source: Authors (2024)

In the model summary shown in Table 3, the model predicted 70% variation in the sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County ($R^2=0.70$). The balance of 30% was due to other factors outside the model. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) data shows that for $p = 0.00$ (<0.05), $F=54$ implying that the model was significant in estimating sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County. From the coefficient summary, the constant for sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County was 0.54. Holding other factors constant, a single-unit increase in each of the M&E Practice namely: capacity building in M&E, funding M&E activities, stakeholders` participation in M&E and dissemination of M&E finding would vary sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County in the following respective magnitudes: 0.11, 0.77, 0.11 and 0.02. This, simplified the research model as follows

$$Y = 0.54 + 0.11X_1 + 0.77X_2 + 0.11X_3 + 0.02X_4 + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

Where:

Y is sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County,

X_1 is capacity building in M&E,

X_2 is funding M&E activities,

X_3 is Stakeholders` participation in M&E,

X_4 is dissemination of M&E findings,

β_0 is constant and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ are determination coefficients for X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4 , respectively and ϵ is term of error.

Discussion

This study explored the relationship between Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) practices (capacity building in M&E, funding M&E activities, stakeholders' participation in M&E, dissemination of M&E findings) and sustainability of building construction projects, focusing on the convention facility at the Kenya School of Government in Embu County, Kenya. The model accounted for 70% variation in the sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County ($R^2=0.70$). This finding indicated that M&E practices significantly contribute to achieving sustainable outcomes of projects. For instance, enhanced capacity contributes to informed decision-making and the early identification of risks, thereby supporting project sustainability (Rogito et al. 2020). Consistent investment and funding of M&E activities contributes to the ability to sustain the project's outcomes (Njeru & Luketero, 2018). Similarly, participation increases alignment of project's objectives with stakeholders' expectations which increases ownership and commitment (Okul & Nyonje, 2020). Sharing M&E findings promotes transparency and accountability while providing valuable insights for continuous improvement in project sustainability. When a project is not delivered within timeline, budget and quality requirements, users are denied opportunities to enjoy project deliverables in time for greater prosperity (PMI, 2021). Thus, it is crucial to prioritize effective M&E practices to ensure that projects are delivered on time, within budget, and meet quality standards.

The correlation analysis showed that funding M&E had very strong and positive relationship with sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County ($r=0.82$). This finding was consistent with past empirical establishment by Murei et al (2017) that budgeting and funding of M&E contributes to high performance of projects. The finding is bolstered by a convergence of research outcomes by Njeru and Luketero (2018) showing that adequate resource allocation to M&E activities increase effectiveness of project. It follows that funding of M&E activities cannot be ignored in the strategies towards building a sustainable project. Theory of sustainability comes into play through the assertion that sustainability will remain an illusion if it's not planned, budgeted and acted for. But project finances are solicited from stakeholders such as sponsors, donors and development partners. According to the tenets of stakeholder theory, good relationship and connection and creating value of stakeholders emboldens the commitment, ownership and support towards project deliverable.

The correlation analysis for capacity building in M&E and sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County revealed a positive but weak relationship ($r= 0.37$). While the relationship is weak, this finding underscores the necessity of strengthening capacity-building programs in M&E to maximize their effectiveness and contribute to more robust project sustainability outcomes. This argument is aligned with empirical findings by Kithinji (2019) that building capacity on project M&E promotes project effectiveness. Further support is based on the finding from a related study by Rogito et al (2020) that capacity building in M&E promotes sustainability of projects. The findings contribute to the theory of sustainability which empathizes on the balance state of society (stakeholders) and economic gains (project value) in order to generate long-lasting benefits (Ekardt, 2014). The finding further support stakeholder theory that when stakeholders are empowered in project activities, it leads to greater positive benefits.

The analysis of the relationship between participation of stakeholder in M&E and sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County revealed a weak but positive relationship ($r = 0.25$). This finding aligns with the findings from an empirical study by Makau et a. (2018) that stakeholder's participation enhances quality of Monitoring and Evaluation outcomes. Moreover, Okul and Nyonje (2020) studied the link between stakeholder involvement in evaluations and utilization of project evaluation findings for program improvement in Kenya and concluded that stakeholder participation increases usability of Monitoring and Evaluation results. While exploring

on the role of stakeholder stakeholders` participation in M&E, Also, Sulemana (2018) found that performance and sustainability of projects increased with participation of stakeholders in M&E processes. This finding is further strengthened by theory of sustainability that delivery of sustainable projects requires collaborative and concerted effort.

The finding on the relationship between dissemination of M&E findings and sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County showed a weak but positive relationship ($r=0.21$). While the strength of relationship of the variables underscore were found to be positively weak, the broader finding rhymes with the research findings by Mutekhele et al (2016) that dissemination and use of monitoring data has insignificant influence on project performance and sustainability. However, this finding contradicts Zulch`s (2014) conclusion that effective project communication on areas of improvement enhances delivery of sustainable outcomes. Nonetheless, both sustainability theory and stakeholder theory were found to have a weak linkage with the finding that dissemination of M&E findings has weak contribution to the sustainability of convention facility project at KSG in Embu County.

Conclusion

The findings from this study highlights the value of investment in comprehensive M&E practices not only as a best practice but a necessity for the sustainability of building construction projects. Specifically, the study emphasizes the integral role of M&E practices namely: capacity building in M&E, funding of M&E activities, stakeholders' participation in M&E and dissemination of M&E findings, in ensuring long-term project success. Capacity building in M&E enhances knowledge and skills leading to informed and sustainable decision-making. Adequate allocation of financial resources or funding of M&E processes ensures effective execution of M&E activities thereby supporting continuous learning and improvement of project longevity. Active involvement of stakeholders during M&E promotes ownership and commitment in achieving sustainable results. Sharing M&E results is also crucial in ensuring transparency and accountability which strengthens the effort and trust in driving sustainable outcomes form a project. Therefore, it is important for organizations to institute robust and feasible M&E frameworks to augment sustainable deliverables in building construction projects. Policymakers and governments should introduce reforms to ensure that M&E processes for development projects are adequately funded while promoting accountability and long-term value. Further researchers could explore the concept M&E practices from non-linear by integrating contextual and structural factors in the model.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- African Development Bank (ADB). (2021). *Building sustainable infrastructure for the future: African Development Bank and World Bank host global roundtable on infrastructure governance*. Avenue Joseph Anoma, Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire.
- Callistus, T., & Clinton, A. (2018). The role of monitoring and evaluation in construction project management. In *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing* (Vol. 722). Springer.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed method approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Devina, M. (2021). Southeast Asia's largest convention center in Indonesia redefines sustainable architecture. Retrieved from <https://synergy.id>
- Ekardt, F. (2014). Climate change, justice, and sustainability: The right to freedom, protection rights, and balancing. *Archiv für Rechts- und Sozialphilosophie*, 100(2), 187–200.
- Juan, M. D. (2020). Strategic planning & innovation, Port Authority of Valencia, Spain.
- Kenya School of Government. (2020). *Proposed convention centre at Kenya School of Government – Embu campus*. Office Printer.
- Kenya School of Government. (2021). *Monitoring and evaluation report for the construction of the convention centre– Embu campus*. Office Printer.
- Kithnji, C. (2019). Evaluation capacity building and improvement of monitoring and evaluation practice among non-governmental organizations in Central Eastern Counties of Kenya. *European Scientific Journal*, 25(8), 177–202.
- Kornei, K. (2020). Opportunities and challenges of virtual meetings. *Eos*, 101. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020EO150222>
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(608). Sage Publishers.
- Kruger, S. E. (2016). *Key success factors in managing a conference center in South Africa* (Unpublished research work).
- Makau, J. N., Mackenzi, I. O., & Nicole, D. (2018). The effect of stakeholders' participation on project monitoring and evaluation. *The Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 5(4), 2222–2229.
- Meneghelli, A. (2018). Whole-building embodied carbon of a North American LEED-certified library: Sensitivity analysis of the environmental impact of building materials. *Building and Environment*, 134, 230–241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2018.03.051>
- Murei, L., Kidombo, H., & Gakuu, C. (2017). Influence of monitoring and evaluation budget on performance of horticulture projects in Nakuru County, Kenya. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom*, 4(12), 620–633.
- Mutekhele, B., Rambo, C., Ongati, O., & Nyonje, R. (2016). Data dissemination and use and performance of educational building construction projects: A case of Bungoma County, Kenya. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 7(10), 51–57.
- Njeru, I. M., & Luketero, S. W. (2018). Influence of monitoring and evaluation strategies on performance of medical camp projects in hospitals in Kenya: A case of Embu North Sub County. *International Academic Journal of Information Sciences and Project Management*, 3(1), 61–73.

- Okul, E. O., & Nyonje, R. O. (2020). Examining stakeholder involvement in the evaluation process for program improvement. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(5), 179–191.
- Project Management Institute (PMI). (2021). *A guide to the project management body of knowledge (PMBOK Guide)* (6th ed.). Newtown Square, PA: Author.
- Rogito, O., Maitho, T., & Nderitu, A. (2020). Capacity building in participatory monitoring and evaluation on sustainability of food security irrigation projects. *Journal of Engineering, Project, and Production Management*, 10(2), 87–94.
- Spector, N., Silvestre, J., Alexander, M., Martin, B., Hooper, J., Squires, A., & Ojemeni, M. (2020). NCSBN regulatory guidelines and evidence-based quality indicators for nursing education programs. *Journal of Nursing Regulation*, 2(2), 52–64.
- Sulemana, M. (2018). An assessment of stakeholders' participation in monitoring and evaluation of district assembly projects and programmes in the Savelugu Nanton Municipality Assembly, Ghana. *Ghana Journal of Development Studies*, 15(1), 173–196.
- Zulch, B. (2014). Project communication in project management. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 119, 172–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.03.020>

